

USE OF MODERN METHODS AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING KOREAN GRAMMAR

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Abstract. *This article discusses the current efforts to teach the Korean language in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *Korean language, innovative technology, technological tools, methods.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДОВ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ КОРЕЙСКОЙ ГРАММАТИКЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются текущие усилия по преподаванию корейского языка в Республике Узбекистан.*

Ключевые слова: *корейский язык, инновационные технологии, технологические инструменты, методы.*

The processes of world globalization, the unprecedented expansion of states, nations and intercultural relations have made the issue of full communication between representatives of different peoples urgent. Full communication includes, first of all, language relations. Knowing a foreign language increases the level of knowledge, expands the worldview, contributes to a more tolerant perception of the surrounding world.

Recently, the rapid development of business and personal relations has expanded the economic and cultural relations of the Republic of South Korea with Uzbekistan and other CIS countries. Last year 2022 marked 30 years since our country established diplomatic relations with the Republic of South Korea. During this period, South Korea and Uzbekistan became worthy partners in the real sense. The demand for learning the Korean language has increased in our country, which was established on the basis of this cooperation. In addition to university education, Korean language teaching is also rapidly developing in various educational institutions outside the university, through Internet networks. In such a situation, the organization of short-term courses using modern methods and pedagogical technologies for different categories of students has become a requirement.

One of the urgent issues of the present time is to educate the young generation through the teaching of foreign languages in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, national pride, high morals and spirituality, pride in our ancient and rich heritage, national and universal values. Fundamental reforms in the world education system promote the problems of creating the necessary conditions for students to learn foreign languages perfectly, to be able to express themselves in all fields knowing a foreign language, and to develop their oral and written speech in a foreign language. Organizations such as UNESCO, UNICEF, Association of European Universities, European Network for Quality Assurance of Higher Education, KOICA, etc. is engaged in. The development of this issue in general trends is of great importance in the formation of modernity and foreign language skills in the young generation, and serves to increase the creative abilities of students in connection with the problems of modern education.

Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, and for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed for the teaching of foreign languages, including Korean, in accordance with the recommendations of the global framework for evaluating the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers (CEFR) and TOPIK (Test of Proficiency in Korean). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, the classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning Korean is also increasing day by day. Korean language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking), and specific concepts and skills are taught in each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning the Korean language.

The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools comes in handy in every aspect of Korean language learning (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, compliance with grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning the Korean language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process, among other things, when using computers, the student can watch and listen to Korean language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; - you can listen to and watch Korean language broadcasts and TV programs. Using audio broadcasts, which is a more traditional method, makes the process of learning Korean more interesting and effective for students.

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